

Gordon, R.M., Shi, Z., Scharff, D.E., Fishkin, R.E., & Shelby, R.D. (2021). An International Survey of the Concept of Effective Psychodynamic Treatment During the Pandemic. *Psychodynamic Psychiatry*, 49,3, 453-462.

An International Survey of the Concept of Effective Psychodynamic Treatment During the Pandemic

Abstract

Introduction: Most psychotherapists had no choice during the COVID-19 pandemic but to offer teletherapy in order to provide needed treatment. Several psychoanalytic theoreticians wondered if the very concept of treatment would change without an embodied relationship in an office setting. **Methods:** To attempt to understand the current concept of effective psychodynamic treatment in the new norm of teletherapy, we surveyed practitioners from 56 countries and regions who remotely treated patients psychodynamically during the beginning months of the pandemic. We asked the practitioners to rank 6 factors felt to be important to psychodynamic treatment: use of the couch during sessions, session in-office or via teletherapy, cultural similarity between therapist and patient, number of sessions a week, patient factors (motivation, insightfulness and high functioning) and therapist factors (empathy, warmth, wisdom and skillfulness). **Results:** We received 1,490 survey responses. As predicted, we found that the therapist and patient variables were considered much more important (both tied as highest rankings) to effective treatment than any of the other variables including if the therapy was in-office or by teletherapy. **Discussion:** Psychodynamic practitioners world-wide confirmed that it is the empathy, warmth, wisdom and skillfulness of the therapist, and the motivation, insightfulness and level of functioning of the patient that is most important to treatment effectiveness regardless if the treatment is remote or embodied.

Keywords: Distance psychodynamic treatment, teleanalysis, teletherapy, on-line treatment, factors in psychoanalysis

Introduction

The COVID-19 Pandemic created a paradigm shift to distance treatment for most practitioners around the world. Despite the favorable research on the effectiveness of distance psychodynamic therapy (Gordon, Wang & Tune, 2015; Gordon & Lan, 2017, Lindegaard, Berg & Andersson 2020), many psychodynamic practitioners have been reluctant to use it as compared to practitioners who favor other theoretical orientations. Perle et al. (2013) in their survey of 717 therapists found that cognitive-behavioral and systems psychologists were significantly more accepting of teletherapy than were psychodynamic/analytic or existential therapists. And more recently, Békés & Aafjes-van Doorn (2020) found that CBT therapists had a more positive attitude towards online therapy compared to psychodynamic psychotherapists.

While any evidence-based talk therapy theoretically can be effective by telecommunications, it is still hotly debated whether psychodynamic distance treatment can be effective. Psychodynamic treatment, it is often argued, requires a therapeutic “presence” that is characterized by more intensity, depth and time than most other psychotherapies since it deals with uncovering issues of personality, attachment and affects that are largely beyond the patient’s conscious awareness. Today, many theoreticians view the psychodynamic paradigm as organized within a complexity theory with the interacting dynamics of attachment, early family relationships, innate urges and temperament, traumas, developmental conflicts, favored defenses, dominant affects, rigid cognitions, and transferences, etc. The issues that arise from these dynamic interactions are mostly implicit and latent requiring a highly attuned practitioner for interventions. The question is frequently raised by those who doubt the effectiveness of distance analytic treatment is if these subtle communications are filtered out in distance work to such a degree that it decreases the effectiveness of the treatment.

Bayles (2012) argued that since the therapeutic action is grounded in implicit, procedural, nonverbal communication the entire body is implicated in the analytic dialogue and that technological modalities limit access to the information communicated via the body. Roesler (2017) wrote that the loss of nonverbal cues has implications for the treatment of patients who have difficulties relying on a secure therapeutic relationship. Emotional security in interactional relationships is transmitted to a much greater extent by nonverbal cues than by verbal content and that psychodynamic methods are specialized to refer to this level of interaction.

However, this same criticism can be lodged against the use of the couch in psychoanalysis where the patients’ facial cues are out of sight. However, many psychoanalysts feel that the wealth of information that comes from patients exploring mental life without the distraction of the analysts’ facial expressions is worth the minor loss of the patients’ facial cues. This lack of bodily cues is replicated with audio-telephonic communication, where there is also less distraction in service to exploring mental life. Spiro & Devenis (1992) examined the use of the telephone in conducting long-term, intensive, psychodynamic psychotherapy and compared it with traditional office contact. They found in many instances that the telephone sessions increased the intensity and duration of the treatment and offered several distinct advantages over in-office contact. In this sense, phone use is similar to the use of the couch, sitting reclined or looking away. Zalusky (1998) wrote that past traditions and prejudices may have precluded many analysts from openly considering the use of telephone analysis as a viable treatment option. Zalusky adds that psychoanalysis by telephone may represent the best treatment available

for a particular patient. Ehrlich (2019) argued that in certain cases, and under certain conditions, extremely useful analytic work can be done on the phone or through videoconferencing. Ehrlich noted that contrary to what some critics of distance psychoanalysis maintain, with patients who are motivated and can make use of analysis, physical distance between analyst and patient and/or occasional technological difficulties do not limit or preclude successful analysis. Wenhua Yan (Ren, Sze, Yan, Shu, Zhongyao & Gordon, in press) wrote that the informality of the online psychodynamic psychotherapy and the opportunity of being in their own space could actually encourage some patients to be more open and willing to express themselves.

However, there are some therapists and patients that feel that without an embodied presence in an office, there can be no real therapy. There is an emotional reaction to being in a care-taker's presence that might matter more to certain personalities than to others. These emotions might affect the degree of comfort with distance treatment, but we have no data yet as to whether this feeling will affect the outcome of treatment.

Moshtagh's (2020) response to this is that, "Being spatially distant poses no contradictions for psychoanalysis, as long as both parties-patient and analyst, supervisee and supervisor, candidate and instructor-are willing to listen, hear, and be heard emotionally."

The research on the effectiveness of distance psychodynamic treatment has implications for understanding the very factors that bring about therapeutic change. Migone (2013) wrote that psychoanalysis over the Internet has implications for the way we think about theory of technique generally, and for what we mean by "communication" between patient and analyst. The way we think about online therapy has meaning for the way we practice "offline" therapy.

How important is the variable of distance treatment as compared to other variables? Many researchers have found that the qualities of the therapist and the patient and their therapeutic alliance were reliably among the most essential factors in predicting outcome. Wampold (2015) reviewed the meta-analysis of the therapist and patient alliance which included nearly 200 studies involving over 14,000 patients. He found that the aggregate correlation between alliance and outcome was equivalent to a Cohen's d of 0.57 (a medium sized effect). More specifically, Wampold reported a meta-analysis of 59 studies with the correlation between the therapists' empathy with treatment outcome, resulting in a relatively large effect ($d = 0.63$). Fisher, Atzil-Slonim, Bar-Kalifa, Rafaeli & Peri (2016) studied 101 patients in psychodynamic psychotherapy and found that the therapeutic alliance and patients' contact with emotions during therapy sessions was effective in reducing their suffering outside of sessions. Additionally, de Jong, et al. (2019) found that the patient variable of insightfulness, significantly increases gains at both post-measurement and follow-up of treatment. Gordon & Lan (2017) surveyed 90 psychodynamic practitioners who had their psychodynamic treatment on-line. They felt that the therapist variables (warmth, wisdom, empathy, and skillfulness) were much more important in the effectiveness of their treatment than whether the treatment was in-office or with videoconferencing (VCON), or because of any issues related to cultural differences.

Fisher, Guralnik, Fonagy & Zilcha-Mano (2020) pointed out that understanding the development of epistemic trust within the therapeutic alliance is significant for the successful transition to videoconferencing treatment. Epistemic trust is defined as the openness to acquiring social

knowledge. It is developed throughout social interactions, beginning early in life, including the infant's experiences with their primary caregivers. Children who successfully established epistemic trust are able to modify their assumptions safely in the light of new information or experiences as adults. Fisher et al stated that as the world is increasingly moving online, it seems important to preserve the characteristics of human communication as we know them from in-person encounters and embrace them as we are going online. That is, the quality of the therapeutic alliance, which is essential for personal growth can be communicated remotely. For those patients with low epistemic trust in videoconferencing sessions, ostensive physical cues such as facial expressions and maintaining eye contact enables the patient to continue acquiring social information that is personally relevant for coping.

This research explores the dramatic change due the pandemic, sheltering in place and physical distancing, and from practitioners who never or infrequently used distance treatment, to it becoming at least temporarily, the "new norm." We hope to learn from this paradigmatic shift how this change has affected the attitudes of psychodynamic practitioners' very concept of what is important to psychodynamic treatment.

There is little known as to how important the issue of teletherapy is in comparison to other therapeutic variables. We want to address the over-arching issue of what psychodynamic practitioners consider most important to therapeutic change in this new world of virtual and embodied relationships.

Methods

Sample

Our methodology employs a large international sample of the opinions of psychodynamic practitioners collected in the early phase of the pandemic. We used populations of convenience from email lists and listservs from the: China American Psychoanalytic Alliance (CAPA); International Psychotherapy Institute; Society for Psychoanalysis and Psychoanalytic Psychology of the American Psychological Association, and the American Psychoanalytic Association. We emailed a link to our Survey Monkey questionnaire and included the following notice: "Please help us with our research: Telepsychotherapy During the 2020 Pandemic. We are considerate of your time, so we kept the survey to less than 4 minutes. If you have recently psychoanalytically treated a patient by telepsychotherapy (i.e., phone, videoconferencing) click on this link:..." All responses were anonymous. The Washington Baltimore Center for Psychoanalysis Institutional Review Board gave full approval to conduct this study.

We realize that there are many important factors that contribute to the effectiveness of psychodynamic treatment. Empirical research can help us weigh their relative importance. There was no existing research to date on if the distance treatment during the pandemic affected their concept of psychodynamic treatment.

We asked our respondents to rank order the following factors in terms of their importance to effective treatment: use of the couch during sessions, session in-office or via teletherapy, cultural similarity between therapist and patient, number of sessions a week, patient factors (motivation, insightfulness and high functioning) and therapist factors (empathy, warmth, wisdom and skillfulness). The order of these factors was roughly presented in the questionnaire in the

opposite order of our hypotheses in order to control for a presentation bias. We predicted that the therapist and patient variables will be considered much more important to effective treatment than any of the other variables including in-office or by teletherapy. We used SPSS to compute focused t tests for two independent samples (Rosnow, and Rosenthal, 2002). To correct for the large sample size, we only reported significant levels $p < .001$.

Results

We received 1,490 completed surveys, from 56 countries and regions. The most reported country or region was the United States (59%), then China (11%), Europe (8%), United Kingdom (4%), Latin America (4%), Canada (3%), and Australia/New Zealand region (2%), Indian Subcontinent (1%), South Africa (1%) and Other (7%).

Distribution across professions: psychologists (46%), counselors (21%), social workers (15%), psychiatrists (12%). Our survey assessed primary theoretical orientation, since some practitioners might treat patients psychodynamically, although they might have another primary theoretical orientation. Psychoanalytic/psychodynamic was by far the most reported primary theoretical orientation (79%). Other orientations include CBT (9%), Humanistic/Existential (6%), Family Systems (2%) and Other (4%). Most of the respondents identified as female (68%; male 31%; not listed and prefer not to answer, 1.5%). The mean age range was 50-59 for the whole sample, with over-all 65% of the sample within the 40-69 age range. Gender and age did not significantly interact with any of the other variables. No surveys were excluded from our data analysis.

Our hypothesis was supported. The therapist and patient variables were considered much more important to effective psychodynamic treatment than any of the other variables including treatment by teletherapy. Psychodynamic practitioners ranked- Therapist Factors (empathy, warmth, wisdom and skillfulness) (ranking of 1 = most effective treatment factor; $M = 2.08$, $SD = 1.45$) and Patient Factors (motivation, insightfulness and high functioning) ($M = 2.18$, $SD = 1.24$) as the most important factors in treatment outcome, much higher than Sessions in-office or teletherapy ($M = 3.55$, $SD = 1.41$). (Sessions in-office or teletherapy vs. Patient Factors $p < .0001$; Sessions in-office or teletherapy vs. Therapist Factors $p < .0001$). All the rankings were significantly different from each other except for Therapist Factors and Patient Factors ($p = .05$), and Sessions in-office or teletherapy and Number of sessions a week ($p < .37$). (See Table 1)

Table 1*“Rank how much each of these factors contribute to the effectiveness of treatment”*

Importance to Effectiveness of Treatment	N	M	SD
Therapist Factors (empathy, warmth, wisdom and skillfulness)	1435	2.08	1.45
Patient Factors (motivation, insightfulness and high functioning)	1347	2.18	1.24
Sessions in-office or teletherapy	1338	3.55	1.41
Number of sessions a week	1369	3.60	1.09
Cultural similarity between therapist and patient	1374	4.35	1.29
Use of the couch during sessions	1348	5.11	1.38

1 = most important to effectiveness, 6 = least important to effectiveness; All comparisons are significantly different ($p < .0001$) except for Therapist Factors and Patient Factors ($p = .05$), and Sessions in-office or teletherapy and Number of sessions a week ($p < .37$).

Discussion

The Covid-19 pandemic was an international crisis, so we wanted a multicultural perspective on the psychodynamic use of teletherapy. Our survey consisted of 1,490 responses from practitioners from 56 countries and regions who remotely treated patients with psychoanalysis or psychodynamic psychotherapy during the early phase of the shelter at home and physical distancing due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Previous research on the effectiveness of teletherapy failed to put the use of teletherapy in the context of other important treatment variables. Instead of simply asking what practitioners thought of teletherapy, we assessed teletherapy within the practitioners' concept of psychodynamic treatment. Over-all, when psychodynamic practitioners were asked to rank order the factors they considered to contribute most to the effectiveness of treatment, both the therapist factors (empathy, warmth, wisdom and skillfulness) and patient factors (motivation, insightfulness and high functioning) were ranked much more important to the effectiveness of psychodynamic treatment than whether the sessions were conducted in-office or via teletherapy, the number of sessions a week, cultural similarity between therapist and patient, or the use of the couch. This we believe is an important finding when considering concerns about various parameters.

Limitations of this study include that it was based on populations of convenience, that is who volunteered to take the survey. We consider that this may be the only ethical methodology for conducting such research. We do not have any reason to suspect that the volunteer nature of the sample would significantly skew the results. The large number of international respondents helps support the reliability of the findings.

There is a need for research on the unconscious meaning of being in the presence of the caregiver. With teletherapy comes the greater availability of treatment across communities and countries, but also new problems. Are there attachment issues and personality traits that are particularly sensitive to the lack of a physical presence of the other? But in the end, psychodynamic practitioners world-wide confirm that it is the empathy, warmth, wisdom and skillfulness of the therapist, and the motivation, insightfulness and level of functioning of the patient that is most important to treatment effectiveness regardless if the treatment is remote or embodied.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank for their assistance in data collection: Tiffany Bryant, Xiubing Wang, Fu Xiaoyu, Wendy Cuiqin, Anna Innes, and Caroline Sehon. We also appreciate the feedback on our survey questions by: John Auerbach, Jacques P. Barber, Barbara Milrod, Paolo Migone, and Anthony F. Tasso. And thanks to Robert F. Bornstein and Kunhae Lee for help with the manuscript. The authors are grateful to the China American Psychoanalytic Alliance for their research grant.

References

- Bayles, M. (2012). Is physical proximity essential to the psychoanalytic process? An exploration through the lens of Skype?. *Psychoanalytic Dialogues*, 22(5), 569-585.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10481885.2012.717043>
- Békés, V. & Aafjes-van Doorn, K. (2020). Psychotherapists' attitudes towards online therapy during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Psychotherapy Integration*, 30(2), 238-247.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/int0000214>
- de Jong, S., Hasson-Ohayon, I., van Donkersgoed, R. J., Timmerman, M. E., van der Gaag, M., Aleman, A., ... & Lysaker, P. H. (2019). Predicting therapy success from the outset: The moderating effect of insight into the illness on metacognitive psychotherapy outcome among persons with schizophrenia. *Clinical psychology & psychotherapy*, 26(6), 650-660. DOI: 10.1002/cpp.2388
- Ehrlich, L. T. (2019). Teleanalysis: Slippery Slope or Rich Opportunity?. *Journal of the American Psychoanalytic Association*, 67(2), 249-279.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0003065119847170>
- Fisher, H., Atzil-Slonim, D., Bar-Kalifa, E., Rafaeli, E., & Peri, T. (2016). Emotional experience and alliance contribute to therapeutic change in psychodynamic therapy. *Psychotherapy*, 53(1), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pst0000041>
- Fisher, S., Guralnik, T., Fonagy, P., & Zilcha-Mano, S. (2020) Let's face it: video conferencing psychotherapy requires the extensive use of ostensive cues, *Counselling Psychology Quarterly*, published online, DOI: 10.1080/09515070.2020.1777535
- Gordon, R.M., Wang, X. & Tune, J. (2015). Comparing Psychodynamic Teaching, Supervision and Psychotherapy Over Video-Conferencing Technology with Chinese Students. *Psychodynamic Psychiatry*, 43 (4), 585-599. doi:10.1521/pdps.2015.43.4.585
- Gordon, R.M., & Lan, J. (2017). Assessing Distance Training: How Well Does It Produce Psychoanalytic Psychotherapists? *Psychodynamic Psychiatry*, 45 (3), 329-341. doi:10.1521/pdps.2017.45.3.329
- Lindegaard, T., Berg, M., & Andersson, G. (2020). Efficacy of Internet-Delivered Psychodynamic Therapy: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Psychodynamic Psychiatry*, 48(4), 437-454.
- Migone, P. (2013). Psychoanalysis on the Internet: A discussion of its theoretical implications for both online and offline therapeutic technique. *Psychoanalytic Psychology*, 30(2), 281.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031507>

- Moshtagh N. (2020). Spatially Distant but Emotionally Close: A Personal Reflection on Psychoanalytic Distance Training. *J Am Psychoanal Assoc*.4:3065120919669. doi: 10.1177/0003065120919669.
- Perle, J. G., Langsam, L. C., Randel, A., Lutchman, S., Levine, A. B., Odland, A. P., ... & Marker, C. D. (2013). Attitudes toward psychological telehealth: Current and future clinical psychologists' opinions of Internet-based interventions. *Journal of clinical psychology*, 69(1), 100-113. DOI: 10.1002/jclp.21912
- Ren, Z., Sze, M.Y.T., Yan, W., Shu, X., Zhongyao, X., & Gordon, R.M. (In press). Future Research from China on Distance Psychoanalytic Training and Treatment, Editor, David E. Scharff, MD., *Psychoanalysis and Psychotherapy in China, A Journal in English and Chinese*, Phoenix Publishing House.
- Roesler, C. (2017). Tele-analysis: the use of media technology in psychotherapy and its impact on the therapeutic relationship. *Journal of Analytical Psychology*, 62(3), 372-394. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-5922.12317>
- Rosnow, R. L., and Rosenthal, R. (2002). Contrasts and correlations in theory assessment. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, 27(1), 66.
- Spiro, R. H., & Devenis, L. E. (1992). Telephone therapy: Enhancement of the psychotherapeutic process. *Psychotherapy in private practice*, 9(4), 31-55.
- Wampold, B. E., & Imel, Z. E. (2015). *The great psychotherapy debate: The evidence for what makes psychotherapy work*. New York, NY: Routledge. doi: 10.1002/wps.20238
- Zalusky, S. (1998). Telephone analysis: Out of sight, but not out of mind. *Journal of the American Psychoanalytic Association*, 46(4), 1221-1242. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00030651980460041601>
- Robert M. Gordon, Ph.D. ABPP in Clinical Psychology and in Psychoanalysis
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1990-8644>,
14041 Bellagio Way, 214, Osprey Florida 34229
rmgordonphd@gmail.com (corresponding author)
610-4170501
- Zhenyu Shi, MD, Ph.D.
Room 404
678 Shaanxi North Road
Shanghai 200200 PR China
zshi.harvard@yahoo.com
(86)13661544202

Attending Psychiatrist at the Shanghai St. Michael Hospital and He Yun Xin Yu Mental Health Service

David E. Scharff, M.D.
6612 Kennedy Drive
Chevy Chase, MD 20815-6504
TEL: 301-951-3630
301 461-2105
davidscharff@theipi.org

David Scharff, M.D. is Chair of the IPA's Committee on Couple and Family Psychoanalysis.

Ralph E. Fishkin, DO
171 Gramercy Road
Bala Cynwyd, PA 19004
rfishkindo@gmail.com
610 613 5291

Ralph E. Fishkin D.O. is a Supervising Analyst of the Psychoanalytic Center of Philadelphia, Clinical Associate Professor of Psychiatry at Thomas Jefferson University, and North American Representative to the Board of Directors of the IPA.

R. Dennis Shelby, MSW, Ph.D.
Professor Emeritus
The Institute for Clinical Social Work
Director of Distance Education
Training and Supervising Analyst at The Chicago Psychoanalytic Institute
180 North Michigan Avenue, Suite 2413
Chicago, Illinois 60601
219-406-0571
rdshelby@icsw.edu